

OCULAR MANIFESTATIONS IN ANKYLOSING SPONDYLITIS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic, progressive, immune-mediated inflammatory disease that primarily affects the spine and sacroiliac joints, and is frequently associated with the HLA-B27 genetic marker. This condition is characterized by inflammation of axial and peripheral joints, resulting in stiffness, pain, and progressive limitation of movement. In addition to articular manifestations, AS may also present extra-articular involvement, with acute anterior uveitis (AAU) being the most common, affecting up to 40% of patients. AAU is clinically manifested by severe ocular pain, photophobia, conjunctival hyperemia, and blurred vision, often occurring recurrently and, in most cases, unilaterally. Diagnosis is established through detailed clinical evaluation, combined with laboratory and imaging tests, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the sacroiliac joints and specific ophthalmologic examinations, which are essential for disease monitoring. **Objective.** To report a case of acute anterior uveitis as an extra-articular manifestation in a 29-year-old male patient

with ankylosing spondylitis, describing its clinical course, diagnostic process, and therapeutic approach. **Methodology.** This is a case report based on medical record review, patient interviews, and analysis of laboratory and imaging exams. Data were collected after obtaining informed consent from the patient, ensuring confidentiality and compliance with ethical principles of clinical research through the signing of the informed consent form (ICF). **Results and Discussion.** The patient presented with severe ocular pain, photophobia, and blurred vision, and was diagnosed with acute anterior uveitis associated with ankylosing spondylitis. Initial treatment included topical corticosteroids to control ocular inflammation and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) for pain relief and joint stiffness. Due to symptom recurrence, biological therapy with an anti-TNF agent was introduced, resulting in significant clinical improvement and absence of new ocular flares. The management of AS requires a multidisciplinary approach, integrating rheumatologists and ophthalmologists for effective control of articular and ocular manifestations (10). Biological therapy has proven effective in reducing systemic inflammation and preventing uveitis relapses, contributing to improved function and quality of life (10). Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment are essential to prevent structural complications such as joint ankylosis and permanent visual sequelae, in addition to minimizing the impact of the disease on functionality and overall well-being. **Conclusion.** Acute anterior uveitis represents a relevant extra-articular manifestation of ankylosing spondylitis and may cause significant visual impairment if not identified and treated promptly. The reported case highlights the importance of integration between rheumatology and ophthalmology for appropriate and individualized disease management. The introduction of biological therapies has modified the prognosis of these patients, reducing inflammation, relapse frequency, and the risk of sequelae. Therefore, early diagnosis and adequate therapeutic intervention are essential to preserve vision and joint mobility, ensuring better quality of life and reducing the systemic impact of the disease.

Keywords: Ankylosing spondylitis. Uveitis. Autoimmune

INTRODUCTION

Spondyloarthritis is a group of inflammatory diseases that share characteristics such as: involvement of the sacroiliac joints, association with the HLA-B27 marker, and the presence of extra-articular manifestations. This large group includes: ankylosing spondylitis (AS), psoriatic arthritis (PsA), enteropathic arthropathies (EA), reactive arthritis (RA), undifferentiated spondyloarthritis (US), and juvenile spondyloarthritis (JS).

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic, progressive, immune-mediated disease,¹ characterized primarily by involvement of the sacroiliac joints, axial skeleton, and entheses.¹ Inflammatory low back pain is peculiar to this group of diseases, with an insidious onset, alternating character, lasting more than 3 months, morning stiffness for more than 30 minutes, which improves with movement in the gluteal region, and may radiate to the posterior aspect of the thigh up to the popliteal fossa.¹ The patient may present with enthesitis, accentuated kyphosis, loss of cervical lordosis, peripheral arthritis,¹³ and, subsequently, "bamboo spine".⁹

Enthesitis is characterized by inflammation of the anchoring point of tendons, ligaments, and capsules to bone tissue, especially those made of fibrocartilage, including the plantar fascia, Achilles tendon, patellar tendon, iliac crests, sacroiliac joints, and spinal ligaments.¹¹ Arthritis has an oligoarticular, asymmetrical, and minimally erosive presentation.¹

In addition to clinical aspects, the recognition and classification of spondyloarthritis have been improved with the introduction of the *Assessment of SpondyloArthritis International Society* (ASAS) parameters. These criteria contribute significantly to the identification of different disease phenotypes, especially in the early stages.²⁹

The ASAS guidelines consider two main forms of presentation: axial and peripheral spondyloarthritis.²⁹ In the axial form, the entry point is the presence of chronic low back pain, with onset before age 45. Classification can be established by demonstrating sacroiliitis on plain radiography or magnetic resonance imaging. In addition, it must be associated with at least one typical clinical feature, such as HLA-B27 antigen positivity, accompanied by two or more clinical manifestations, such as inflammatory low back pain, enthesitis, dactylitis, uveitis, psoriasis, inflammatory bowel disease, family history, or a favorable response to nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.²⁹

In peripheral spondyloarthritis, the initial finding is the presence of oligoarthritis, enthesitis, or dactylitis. Classification can be made by the association between HLA-B27 positivity and two clinical characteristics, or by demonstrating sacroiliitis on imaging or elevated inflammatory markers, associated with at least one compatible clinical manifestation.

30

These assessment patterns allow for greater precision in characterizing the spectrum of spondyloarthritis, reinforcing the heterogeneity of its presentations and facilitating the recognition of axial and peripheral forms, especially in the early stages.³⁰ Thus, the diagnostic proposals of ASAS complement the clinical examination, laboratory and imaging findings, providing a robust framework for rheumatological evaluation.

The prevalence of aortic sclerosis (AS) is 0.1%–1.4% of the world population, more common in males (3:1 ratio), in Caucasian individuals, with symptoms appearing before the age of 45. There is a strong association with the HLA-B27 antigen, present in 88% to 96%, especially in the axial form. Approximately 90% of patients with axial AS are HLA-B27 positive, highlighting the role of this immunogenetic marker in susceptibility to the disease. In first-degree relatives, the prevalence is higher, ranging from 5% to 7%, reinforcing the genetic role.

In terms of pathophysiology, it is characterized by the infiltration of CD4 and CD8 T

lymphocytes and macrophages into the entheses, associated with the action of cytokines such as TNF- α and TGF- β , which promote inflammation, fibrosis, and ossification, resulting in significant functional loss.¹ Chronic inflammation of the vertebral ligaments leads to the formation of syndesmophytes and ankylosis, characterizing the classic "bamboo spine".¹⁹

Bone neoformation occurs primarily at the entheses, perpetuating the cycle of injury, inflammation, and repair, with prostaglandin E₂ participating in the formation of syndesmophytes.^{20,21} HLA-B27, an MHC class I antigen, presents peptides and CD8 T lymphocytes, and its abnormal folding can form dimers that stimulate IL-23 production.^{23,24} This promotes the differentiation of Th17 lymphocytes, which release IL-17 and intensify inflammation via IL-1 and TNF- α .^{23,24} In genetically predisposed individuals, enthesal inflammation maintains a continuous cycle of injury and repair, characterizing the pathogenesis of AS.²⁵

Anterior scleritis (AS) can present with extra-articular manifestations, such as ocular involvement and cardiovascular conditions like aortic insufficiency, among others.¹¹ The most common extra-articular manifestation is anterior uveitis, present in 40% of patients, usually related to HLA-B27 marker positivity.^{14,9}

Uveitis can affect both segments of the eye, with the anterior segment being the most affected. Most commonly affected, it has a sudden onset, recurrent course, and is unilateral.¹³ Ocular involvement in AS can include the sclera, episclera, uveal tract, and other adjacent structures such as the vitreous humor, retina, optic nerve, and blood vessels.⁴ Uveitis can also be bilateral and is related to disease progression,⁴ presenting an alternating pattern.³

Anterior uveitis associated with HLA-B27 presents with inflammation restricted to the uvea (the middle vascular layer of the eye),³ whose symptoms manifest as ocular pain, reduced visual acuity, photophobia, and limbal hyperemia, which are markers of disease severity and activity.^{6,3,4}

A large proportion of patients with acute uveitis are seen in the emergency department, where the type of uveitis, its location, clinical course, and laterality are initially categorized based on the international classification *Uveitis Study Group*, ruling out the possibility of a primary ophthalmological disease. The medical history and physical examination provide information about sex, age, origin, and history of systemic diseases, such as arthritis, gastrointestinal diseases, venereal infections, dermatological conditions and central nervous system disorders, which may be associated with uveitis.

Blurred vision is the main symptom of acute anterior uveitis (AAU), caused by ciliary spasm and the presence of cells and/or enlargement in the anterior chamber of the eye; pain,

redness, and tearing are the other main symptoms. Episodes of photophobia and keratic precipitates, hypopyon, pupillary membrane, and hyphema are part of the clinical picture, the most common ocular complications being cataracts (9.7%) and glaucoma (4.8%). Clinical evaluation by an ophthalmologist is of paramount importance in establishing the diagnosis of uveitis in patients.

The standard protocol for patients with a primary episode of uveitis consists of ordering a complete blood count, biochemistry, ESR, urinalysis, syphilis serology, tuberculin skin test (PPD), and chest X-ray. In cases of recurrent non-granulomatous uveitis, imaging studies such as X-rays of the sacroiliac joints and spine are essential. Subsequently, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the sacroiliac joints may be requested in cases where no abnormalities are detected on plain radiography, in addition to HLA-B27 testing.

In patients with uveitis, clinical evaluation by an ophthalmologist is of paramount importance,¹⁰ with its diagnosis based on clinical history, physical ocular examination, and slit-lamp examination.¹⁵ The latter allows classification of the anatomical location of the uveitis and grading of anterior chamber inflammation, visualizing inflammatory cells and proteinaceous exudate.¹⁵

Corneal topography helps monitor disease activity, reflecting changes in corneal thickness during inflammation and treatment.¹⁶ In AS, macrovascular changes, such as atherosclerosis, are evident, while microvascular changes are poorly studied. Furthermore, retinal vascular parameters can be assessed in an accessible and non-invasive way, by fundus photography.¹⁷

Treatment of acute aortic stenosis (AAU) requires an individualized approach, considering the severity, etiology, and therapeutic response of each patient. Topical corticosteroids are fundamental in the acute phase of ocular inflammation, providing rapid symptom control. However, prolonged use is associated with significant complications such as secondary glaucoma, cataracts, and iris atrophy.^{10, 12}

The international guidelines from ASAS-EULAR recommend that the treatment of AS prioritize the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), biological agents, and intra-articular glucocorticoids, the latter reserved only for specific situations.¹⁹ The use of systemic corticosteroids has a limited role in the management of AS and is not routinely indicated, as there is no evidence of sustained benefit on axial inflammation, and it also presents a considerable risk of adverse metabolic, cardiovascular, and osteoarticular effects.^{119, 2⁸}

Systemic nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) act by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis, potentially reducing the frequency of inflammatory episodes and

constituting an effective alternative to systemic glucocorticoids.^{11,3} Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) have proven useful in cases of uveitis, as well as in peripheral involvement.^{10,14,15}

Biological DMARDs are composed of monoclonal antibodies that modulate the pro- and anti-inflammatory components of the immune system.¹¹ Tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF), a pro-inflammatory cytokine, plays a central role in AS, as elevated levels of this molecule have been detected in the aqueous humor and inflamed joints of patients.¹⁰ TNF inhibitors, such as infliximab and adalimumab, have proven safe and effective for both the management of AS and its ocular manifestations, reducing the recurrence of acute aortic uveitis (AAU).¹⁰ Certolizumab, another TNF antagonist, has also demonstrated a safe and effective profile in the treatment of AS with recurrent uveitis, significantly decreasing the rate of exacerbations.¹⁴

This study presents a case report of ocular manifestations in ankylosing spondylitis (AS), a chronic inflammatory disease, with anterior uveitis being the most common extra-articular involvement.

This study is justified by the need to expand knowledge about ocular manifestations in ankylosing spondylitis (AS), an inflammatory pathology that presents with acute optic neuritis (AONA) as its most common extra-articular manifestation. In this context, early recognition and appropriate therapeutic measures are essential in cases of this nature.

METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive case report study, conducted through observation and detailed recording of the clinical evolution of a patient with ankylosing spondylitis, treated at the infusion clinic of the Oswaldo Cruz University Hospital, from May 2023 to March 2025.

The data were collected through analysis of medical records, patient interviews, and direct observation during clinical follow-up. The information obtained includes:

- Patient identification (initials, age and sex, preserving anonymity);
- Clinical history and relevant background;
- Signs and symptoms presented;
- Additional tests performed;
- Therapeutic approaches adopted;
- Evolution and outcome of the case.

To preserve the patient's privacy and dignity, data that could identify them have been

omitted, in accordance with ethical standards for research involving human subjects (CNS Resolution No. 466/2012). This report was prepared after authorization was granted.

This case report was prepared in accordance with the ethical principles governing research involving human subjects, as per Resolution No. 466/2012 of the National Health Council. The patient's identity was preserved, guaranteeing the confidentiality of information and respect for privacy. All data presented were collected from medical records and clinical files, and were used exclusively for academic and scientific purposes.

The patient was informed about the purpose of disclosing the case and authorized the use of the information through a free and informed consent form. It is emphasized that no additional interventions were performed beyond those necessary for healthcare.

As this is a case report, the study does not present additional risks to those involved, being limited to the description of a clinical situation already experienced in the context of professional practice.

The project was submitted to and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Uninassau Olinda (CAAE: 87117625.5.0000.0408), following the guidelines of CNS Resolution 466/2012.

CASE REPORT

Male patient, 29 years old, born and residing in Timbaúba, diagnosed with HLA-B27 positive spondyloarthritis since 2018.

The clinical history began in 2017 with episodes of diarrhea, followed by hyperemia and pain in the right eye. The patient sought an ophthalmologist in their city, who prescribed symptomatic treatment, without improvement. A few weeks later, the patient developed arthritis in the right knee and ankle, presenting with difficulty walking.

The patient remained under investigation for eight months without a definitive diagnosis being established. During this period, NSAIDs and corticosteroid eye drops were used, but without significant clinical improvement . During this time, the patient began to experience progression of joint pain to the lower limbs, specifically on the left side of the body, including pain and hyperemia in both eyes, morning stiffness lasting more than an hour, and inflammatory lower back pain.

All information pertaining to the period prior to the definitive diagnosis was not recorded in the patient's medical record at Hospital Oswaldo Cruz (HUOC/UPE), including the duration of corticosteroid and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug use. This data was obtained

through a direct interview with the patient.

After a year of disease progression, he was referred to the Rheumatology service at the Oswaldo Cruz University Hospital (HUOC/UPE), where he underwent plain radiography of the sacroiliac joints, which showed erosions and blurring of the articular surfaces. Subsequently, he underwent magnetic resonance imaging of the sacroiliac joints, which showed erosions with normal joint space, elevated inflammatory markers, and a positive HLA B27 test.

He began treatment with Methotrexate, and subsequently, Infliximab was added, administered as bimonthly infusions, with a good clinical response in terms of joint and eye involvement. After this, the patient returned to his work activities and currently works as a salesperson. He experienced flare-ups, generally around the time of the infusion, with recurrent uveitis followed by lower back pain, but at the moment, he is experiencing a good reduction in symptoms.

In April 2024, the participant in this report attended an ophthalmological consultation, during which retinography and corneal topography examinations were performed. The results showed synechiae of the iris with the lens in the right eye, perceptible without dilation [Figure 1] and with greater clarity after pupil dilation [Figure 2]. On fundus examination, visualization was difficult due to shadowing caused by the synechiae of the iris with the lens [Figure 3]. Corneal topography on the right eye showed band keratopathy [Figure 4]. On the left side, fundus examination [Figure 5] and corneal topography [Figure 6] were within normal limits.

The patient requires regular ophthalmological follow-up to monitor eye health and prevent possible synechiae.

Currently, the patient remains on Infliximab, with a good clinical response and a reduction in the frequency of attacks related to both the underlying disease and episodes of uveitis.

Figure 1. Presence of synechiae between the iris and the lens. Image captured before pupil dilation during slit-lamp examination.

Source: Personal archive (2024)

Figure 2. Presence of synechiae between the iris and the lens. Image captured after pupil dilation during a slit-lamp examination.

Source: Personal archive (2024)

Figure 3. In right eye retinography, the technical difficulty of capturing a good image is noticeable, given the shadowing caused by the synechiae of the iris with the lens.

Source : personal archive (2024)

Figure 4. Corneal topography of the right eye. Patients with recurrent anterior uveitis may also present with corneal abnormalities, notably "band keratopathy".

Source : Personal archive (2024)

Figure 5. Retinography in the left eye within normal limits.

Source: Personal archive (2024)

Figure 6. Corneal topography of the left eye. Corneal topography examination, demonstrating a regular surface without sequelae compatible with keratopathy, according to the clean and transparent appearance of the cornea in the biomicroscopy examination.

Source: Personal archive (2024)

DISCUSSION

Acute anterior uveitis (AAU) is the most common extra-articular manifestation of ankylosing spondylitis (AS), affecting between 25% and 40% of patients during the course of the disease.^{12,14}

It presents unilaterally, recurrently, and alternately, manifesting with eye pain, photophobia, and reduced visual acuity.^{2, 5} The reported case illustrates this classic characteristic, since the patient, who has ankylosing spondylitis and is HLA-B27 positive, presented recurrent episodes of anterior uveitis from the onset of the condition.

The pathophysiology of uveitis associated with ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is strongly related to the presence of the HLA-B27 antigen, identified in up to 90% of patients with the axial form of the disease.³ This allele predisposes to an aberrant immune response, with activation of T lymphocytes and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-17, which promote ocular and articular inflammation.¹¹ In the case presented, the persistence of uveitis episodes even under biological treatment reflects the immunological complexity of the disease and the possible participation of environmental factors of the intestinal microbiota in perpetuating the inflammatory response.^{1, 4, 11}

The diagnosis of AAU is based on detailed clinical and ophthalmological evaluation, with emphasis on anterior segment biomicroscopy (slit lamp), which allows the identification of inflammatory cells in the anterior chamber and keratic precipitates.⁷ In the present report, retinography and corneal topography examinations were fundamental to document the complications associated with recurrent ocular inflammation.^{15,16} Retinography showed synechiae of the iris with the lens in the right eye (Figure 1), a characteristic finding of recurrent ocular inflammations, while corneal topography revealed band keratopathy (Figure 4), a consequence of subepithelial calcific deposits secondary to chronic inflammation of the anterior segment.¹⁷ These findings reinforce the importance of periodic ophthalmological evaluation and the use of complementary imaging examinations for monitoring the disease and preventing structural sequelae.⁷

The temporal correlation between uveitis flares and joint activity is variable.⁶ In the patient presented, it was observed that ocular episodes tended to occur close to the date of infliximab infusions, suggesting a possible temporary reduction in the effectiveness of the biological agent at the end of the therapeutic cycle. This observation is relevant because studies demonstrate that adjustments in the interval or dose of TNF inhibitors can reduce the frequency

of ocular relapses.^{10, 13}

Despite presenting with diarrhea, the patient did not exhibit clinical signs suggestive of intestinal inflammatory disease, nor were there any constitutional symptoms that would suggest intestinal involvement in the presentation of AS. Several studies show a strong correlation between spondyloarthritis and inflammatory bowel disease.³¹

Diagnostic delay remains one of the main challenges in ankylosing spondylitis, ranging from 5 to 10 years after the onset of symptoms.¹⁵ In the case described, the patient remained under the care of orthopedists and ophthalmologists for 8 months, using NSAIDs and intraocular corticosteroids, without sustained improvement, until being referred to rheumatology, where the definitive diagnosis was established after one year of disease progression. This course demonstrates how recurrent aortic stenosis can represent an early opportunity for clinical suspicion of AS, allowing for faster intervention and prevention of structural damage.¹⁶

Treatment of aortic uveitis aims to control inflammation and prevent complications such as posterior synechiae, glaucoma, and cataracts.² In this case, the use of infliximab provided a good systemic clinical response, with a reduction in morning stiffness and improved functional capacity, although ocular manifestations persist intermittently. This pattern is consistent with reports in the literature, which demonstrate that TNF inhibitors significantly reduce the incidence and recurrence of uveitis, although not all patients achieve complete remission.^{10,13}

In summary, this report reinforces the importance of an integrated approach between rheumatology and ophthalmology in the management of AS with ocular involvement. Early recognition of ophthalmological manifestations, the judicious use of complementary examinations such as biomicroscopy, retinography, and corneal topography, and continuous monitoring are fundamental to preventing visual complications and optimizing the patient's quality of life.^{26,27}

Despite the inherent limitations of a single case and the short follow-up period, this report contributes to the literature by highlighting the correlation between articular and ocular inflammatory activity, as well as the importance of early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management of ankylosing spondylitis.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The authors conclude that early diagnosis and individualized treatment are essential for patients with uveitis, whether or not associated with ankylosing spondylitis (AS). Regular clinical follow-up, combined with the appropriate use of topical, systemic, and immunomodulatory therapies, proved fundamental for controlling inflammation and preventing complications. Furthermore, this case reinforces the relevance of a multidisciplinary approach, involving ophthalmology and rheumatology, to optimize clinical outcomes. Further studies are needed to consolidate the best therapeutic strategies and expand knowledge about the evolution of the disease and its ocular manifestations.

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